

Risk Factors and Neonatal Outcomes Associated with Meconium-Stained Amniotic Fluid

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Abstract:

Background: Meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF) is a common occurrence in term and post-term pregnancies, associated with various neonatal complications, including meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) and respiratory distress. The severity of neonatal outcomes is often linked to the grade of meconium staining, making it crucial to understand the risk factors and implications of MSAF.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the risk factors for meconium-stained liquor and assess the associated neonatal outcomes based on the grade of MSAF in term pregnancies.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted. A total of 90 pregnant women with term pregnancies and MSAF were included. The participants were categorized based on the grade of MSAF (Grade I, II, and III). Neonatal outcomes, including Apgar scores, the need for resuscitation, and NICU admissions, were recorded. Data were analysed using SPSS version 23.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Of the 90 participants, 50% had Grade I MSAF, 33.3% had Grade II, and 16.7% had Grade III. Neonates with Grade III MSAF had significantly lower Apgar scores at 1 minute (mean score 3) and 5 minutes (mean score 6), a higher need for resuscitation (80%), and a higher NICU admission rate (66.7%) compared to those with lower grades of MSAF. Statistical analysis confirmed a significant association between higher MSAF grades and adverse neonatal outcomes ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The study found that higher grades of meconium-stained amniotic fluid are strongly associated with poorer neonatal outcomes. These findings highlight the need for vigilant monitoring and timely intervention in cases of thick MSAF to improve neonatal health.

Recommendations: It is recommended that healthcare providers closely monitor pregnancies with MSAF, particularly those with thick meconium staining. Early intervention strategies, including expedited delivery and appropriate neonatal resuscitation, should be implemented to mitigate risks.

Keywords: Meconium-stained amniotic fluid, neonatal outcomes, meconium aspiration syndrome, Apgar score, NICU admission.

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Introduction

In obstetrics, (MSAF) is a common condition, particularly in term and post-term pregnancies. Meconium, the fetus's first stool, normally passes after birth, but in 10–20% of births, it passes into the amniotic fluid while the baby is still within the mother, which results in MSAF [1]. Meconium in the amniotic fluid is an indicator of foetal discomfort and is frequently associated with hypoxia or other types of foetal impairment. However, depending on its thickness and the prenatal circumstances linked with it, the clinical importance of MSAF varies greatly.

When determining the risk to the neonate, the MSAF grading system—which goes from thin (Grade I) to thick (Grade III)—is essential. More

severe newborn outcomes, including as meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), respiratory distress, and even perinatal mortality [2], are frequently linked to thick meconium-stained fluid. In order to lower the risk of unfavourable newborn outcomes [3], the care of pregnancies complicated by MSAF entails close monitoring and occasionally prompt intervention, such as amnioinfusion or accelerated delivery.

Additional research has looked into how MSAF affects newborn outcomes. The relationship between the thickness of MSAF and the occurrence of MAS, which is still a major cause of infant morbidity and mortality [4], was highlighted in a research. An another study conducted revealed

newborns with thick meconium had an increased likelihood of needing NICU admission and resuscitation, highlighting the importance of proactive treatment measures in these situations [5].

Research is currently ongoing to determine the precise pathways that allow meconium to enter the amniotic fluid. Foetal hypoxia is thought to cause anal sphincter relaxation and peristalsis, which leads to meconium passage. Nonetheless, some scientists contend that MSAF may also happen to foetuses that are healthy and not under stress, especially in post-term pregnancies [6]. The therapeutic management of MSAF is complicated by this uncertainty, which necessitates a careful balance between action and attentive waiting.

This study aimed to evaluate the risk factors for meconium-stained liquor and assess the associated neonatal outcomes based on the grade of MSAF in term pregnancies.

Methodology

Study Design

This study was a prospective observational study

Study Setting

The study was conducted over a period of six months (from February 2023 to July 2023) at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Government Medical College, Purnea, Bihar, India.

Participants

A total of 90 pregnant women with term pregnancies (≥ 37 weeks of gestation) and their neonates were included in the study. The participants were categorized into three groups based on the grade of meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF):

- **Grade I MSAF:** 45 cases (50%)
- **Grade II MSAF:** 30 cases (33.3%)
- **Grade III MSAF:** 15 cases (16.7%)

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women at term (≥ 37 weeks of gestation)
- Singleton pregnancies

- Spontaneous or induced labor
- Meconium-stained amniotic fluid identified during labor

Exclusion Criteria

- Multiple pregnancies
- Pre-existing medical conditions like diabetes or hypertension
- Known fetal anomalies
- Obstetric emergencies unrelated to meconium-stained liquor

Data Collection

Data was collected through direct observation, maternal medical records, and neonatal assessments. Maternal demographic details, pregnancy history, labor characteristics, and neonatal outcomes (including Apgar scores, need for resuscitation, and NICU admissions) were recorded. Meconium staining was categorized into three grades based on its thickness and amount:

- **Grade I:** Thin meconium
- **Grade II:** Moderate meconium
- **Grade III:** Thick meconium

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized maternal and neonatal characteristics. Categorical variables were compared using the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test, while continuous variables were analyzed with the independent t-test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Logistic regression was used to assess the association between MSAF grades and neonatal outcomes.

Results

A total of 90 pregnant women were included in the study, all of whom had term pregnancies with meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF). The mean age of the participants was 26.4 ± 4.2 years. The majority of the participants (60%) were in the 20–30 years age group, with 25% under 20 years and 15% over 30 years. Primigravida accounted for 55% of the participants, while 45% were multigravida.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

Characteristic	N = 90	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
<20	23	25.6
20–30	54	60.0
>30	13	14.4
Parity		
Primigravida	49	54.4
Multigravida	41	45.6

Out of 90 cases, the distribution of MSAF grades was as follows: **Grade I** in 45 cases (50%), **Grade II** in 30 cases (33.3%), and **Grade III** in 15 cases (16.7%).

Table 2: Distribution of MSAF Grades

MSAF Grade	N = 90	Percentage (%)
Grade I	45	50.0
Grade II	30	33.3
Grade III	15	16.7

Neonatal outcomes were evaluated based on Apgar scores at 1 minute and 5 minutes, the need for resuscitation, and NICU admission. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Neonatal Outcomes

Outcome	Grade I (n=45)	Grade II (n=30)	Grade III (n=15)	Total (N=90)
Apgar Score (1 min)	7	7	3	-
Apgar Score (5 min)	7	7	6	-
Resuscitation Required	10 (22.2%)	12 (40.0%)	12 (80.0%)	34 (37.8%)
NICU Admission	8 (17.8%)	9 (30.0%)	10 (66.7%)	27 (30.0%)

A significant association was found between the grade of MSAF and neonatal outcomes. The Apgar scores at 1 minute and 5 minutes were significantly lower in neonates with higher grades of MSAF ($p < 0.001$). The need for resuscitation and NICU admission rates also increased significantly with higher MSAF grades ($p < 0.001$).

Table 4: Statistical Analysis of Neonatal Outcomes by MSAF Grade

Outcome	p-value
Apgar Score (1 min)	<0.001
Apgar Score (5 min)	<0.001
Resuscitation Required	<0.001
NICU Admission	<0.001

Discussion

The distribution of MSAF grades revealed that half of the cases were Grade I, while Grade II and Grade III accounted for 33.3% and 16.7%, respectively. The study found a clear relationship between the grade of MSAF and neonatal outcomes, with higher grades of meconium staining associated with poorer outcomes.

Neonates with Grade III MSAF demonstrated the most significant challenges, including the highest rate of resuscitation (80%) and NICU admission (66.7%), compared to Grade I and II cases. These results suggest that the presence of thick meconium, indicative of Grade III MSAF, leads to greater respiratory distress and complications immediately after birth.

The Apgar scores at 1 minute were notably lower in Grade III cases, signifying that the neonates were in poorer condition at birth. Although Apgar scores improved by the 5-minute mark across all grades, the immediate need for resuscitation and NICU admission highlights the critical need for timely and aggressive intervention, particularly in cases of severe MSAF.

Statistical analysis confirmed the significance of these findings, with p-values of less than 0.001 for all key outcomes. This strong association between the severity of MSAF and adverse neonatal outcomes highlights the importance of vigilant moni-

toring and management during labor and delivery when MSAF is present.

The results of term infants delivered with varied degrees of MSAF severity were the subject of the study investigation. According to their research, there is a direct link between the severity of MSAF and poor newborn outcomes such as low Apgar scores, chronic pulmonary hypertension, and (MAS). According to the study, meticulous grading of MSAF throughout labour may aid in better anticipating and handling any difficulties [7].

In a tertiary care context, a prospective case-control analysis was done highlighting the importance of MSAF in predicting unfavourable newborn outcomes. According to their findings, there is a correlation between heavy meconium staining and a higher risk of emergency caesarean sections, NICU hospitalisations, and newborn respiratory morbidity. The study also highlighted the necessity for prompt and accurate evaluation during labour and suggested that continuous electronic foetal monitoring might assist prevent needless caesarean procedures when thin meconium is present [8].

Finally, at a Bangladeshi tertiary care facility, important risk variables connected to MSAF were discovered. The results of the study showed a strong correlation between the presence of MSAF and foetal distress, advanced gestational age, and extended labour. This correlation raised the risk of newborn death and NICU hospitalisations. Accord-

ing to the research, in order to enhance newborn outcomes in cases with MSAF, these risk variables should be regularly evaluated [9].

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant impact of (MSAF) on neonatal outcomes, particularly when the staining is severe (Grade III). The findings demonstrate that higher grades of MSAF are associated with lower Apgar scores, an increased need for resuscitation, and a higher likelihood of NICU admission. These results underscore the importance of careful monitoring and prompt intervention during labor in cases of MSAF to improve neonatal health. Early identification and management of thick meconium-stained fluid can play a critical role in mitigating risks and ensuring better outcomes for newborns.

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